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Magnetotelluric Monitoring of Fluid Movements in the Cascadia Margin Mantle Wedge and Crust During Episodic Tremor and Slip Events: A Feasibility Study

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Magnetotelluric Monitoring of Fluid Movements in the Cascadia Margin Mantle Wedge and Crust During Episodic Tremor and Slip Events: A Feasibility Study

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Final Report

Abstract: The research project undertaken under CRESCENT Seed Grant funding examined the role of redistribution of fluids in episodic tremor and slip (ETS) phenomena along subduction zone plate boundaries. Current seismological data from western Washington suggests that ETS events, repeating at intervals of 12 to 18 months, may correspond with fluid release from metamorphic reactions within the subducting slab at depths of 30-40 km. These fluids are hypothesized to facilitate a transition from shallow stick-slip to deeper stable sliding earthquake behavior, with an intermediate zone of regular, low-frequency seismic activity. Although seismic evidence implies fluid involvement, direct measurements of these fluids and their migration remain unattained. This study carried out numerical modeling to establish if continuous monitoring of the Cascadia margin with a distributed array of magnetotelluric (MT) instruments designed to measure the continuously changing electric and magnetic fields at each measurement location, a method particularly sensitive to the presence and distribution of subsurface fluids and to the fabric of the intergranular fluid/rock network, would be sensitive to changes in electrical resistivity structure associated with the release and movement of fluids deep in the mantle wedge, as well as to changes in the strain field within the fluid/rock matrix. In addition, we examined the sensitivity of quantities derived from the MT measurements, most notably the MT phase tensor, to the subtle realignment of fluidic channels within the base of the mantle wedge immediately above the slab interface. Pre-, syn- and post-seismic and ...-slip changes in the strain tensor are posited to lead to bulk distortion of the intragranular network fluid channels at the micro-scale, as well as to fluid-filled crack and faults at the macro-scale.

The project established that fluid pulses at and immediately above the slab interface, as well as changes in the mineral grain packing density and/or changes in the bulk orientation of fluidic channels including at the mineral grain boundary scale can plausibly lead to detectable changes in MT derived parameters measured by arrays of MT monitoring instruments installed along the Cascadia margin. Such phenomena may be associated with ETS events, as well as serving as precursors to larger subduction zone earthquake events. This approach suggests the utility of continuous MT array observations, especially when complemented by seismic data, in tracking the migrations and effects of slab-origin fluids during ETS episodes, thereby **directly addressing the CRESCENT pillar priorities FL1, C3S4, and C3S5** and accomplishing the main goal of this project.

Highlighted Results

The magnetotelluric (MT) method employs passive, time-domain measurements of naturally occurring temporal and spatial changes in the Earth's electric (E) and magnetic (H) fields measured at ground level at a series of locations defining a survey array. The measured E and H fields contain the signature of electric currents within the Earth's subsurface generated through electromagnetic induction in response to time-varying E and H fields in the ionosphere and atmosphere generated by space weather and global lightning. The intensity and directional polarization of the induced E and H fields is a sensitive indicator of the electrical conductivity structure (1/resistivity) within the geologic formations beneath and adjacent to the MT survey array. The time-series measurements of the vector E and H fields are transformed into the frequency domain, and MT response functions are derived at each survey location.

The MT response functions vary with the frequency ($=1/\text{period}$) of the variations in the electric and magnetic fields, with progressively lower frequency (longer period) response functions sensitive to the electrical conductivity (1/resistivity) structure over progressively deeper volumes of the Earth below the surface. MT response functions include the frequency-dependent MT impedance tensor (the relationship between E and H), MT induction vectors (the relationship between the vertical component of H to its horizontal components), and the MT phase tensor, a quantity sensitive and indicative of the dimensionality, e.g. whether the electrical structure varies in 1-D, 2-D or 3-D, and of the directional orientation of the electric currents induced at each location in the subsurface by the inducing magnetic "source" fields.

Empirical scaling relationships represent the electrical conductivity (1/resistivity) of a porous material composed of solid grains with intragranular boundaries coated or pores filled with fluids of a given conductivity. At shallow

depths, such as in marine and near-surface saturated sediments, electronic conduction across the solid grains is negligible compared to electrolytic conduction through the pores.

Figure 1. Electrical conduction in geologic materials is both a material bulk property, and a crystal grain boundary property. Bulk conduction depends on rock composition and temperature, and to a lesser extent on pressure, whereas grain boundary conduction is strongly influenced by fluids (interconnected saline fluids, partial melt, volatiles, graphite, hydrogen diffusivity).

Archie’s Law (Archie, 1942) is most commonly used to represent the electrolytic conduction:

$$\sigma = \phi^m \sigma_f, \quad (1)$$

Where σ is the bulk electrical conductivity of the rock/fluid matrix, σ_f is the conductivity ($1/\rho_f$) of the electrolytic fluid, ϕ is the porosity of the medium, and the constant m (“cementation factor”) depends on the shape and connectivity of the pores, where $m \approx 1$ for interconnected, low aspect ratio cracks, $m \approx 2$ for poorly connected, high aspect ratio cracks. In the higher lithostatic pressure of the mid-crust, intermediate geometries hold where $m \approx 1.5$.

Figure 2. Graphical illustration of Archie’s Law showing relationship between porosity (x-axis) and cementation factor (y-axis), with greater cementation factor representing tighter packing between mineral grains.

The relationship between bulk conduction and the product of porosity and intragranular fluid conductivity follows the power law relationship in Equation (1), where for a given porosity the greater the cementation factor, the lower the conductivity. At some critical grain packing level, the aspect of the grains is strongly elliptical and interconnections between fluidic channels are effectively lost, at which point the fluid conductivity no longer contributes to the bulk conduction of the solid-fluid matrix. A modified form of Archie’s Law that describes this transitional domain is: $\sigma = \sigma_g + \phi^2(\sigma_e - \sigma_g)$, where σ_g is the conductivity of the grains.

In the present study, we investigated the following scenarios, using adjustments to the cementation factor (above) to represent changes in fluid distributions as well as distortions in the fluidic network related to

changes in the strain field. We considered such changes over a range of geographic areas, with scales as large as the north-south extent of the subduction margin, and as localized as several tens of km north-to-south. Specifically, for each of the test cases we simulated we considered:

- 1) Bulk changes in fluid volume and distribution – fluid overpressuring as a “lubricant” along the interface (or fluid chemistry over long term) and/or
- 2) Distortions in the fabric of interconnected channels along grain boundaries – $\Delta\sigma, \tau$ {stress changes} $\rightarrow \Delta\varepsilon, \gamma$ {strain changes, i.e. compression, shearing, rotation, channel orientation}.

We use as a baseline model, the 3-D electrical resistivity model from Egbert, G.D., et al., 2022¹, which was obtained through inversion of the land and seafloor MT data set (Figure 4) collected under an NSF projects EAR1053632 (PI: A. Schultz, Co-PIs, G. Egbert, P. Bedrosian), and EAR1459067 (PI: Key, K.), plus data from various legacy projects that are in the public domain.

The ETS zone resistivity can be modeled as a function of porosity and cementation factor (controlled by permeability) calculated with Archie’s Law. Cascadia ETS zone resistivity constrains the porosity between 0 –

¹ Egbert, G.D., B. Yang, P.A. Bedrosian, K. Key, D.W. Livelybrooks, A. Schultz, A. Kelbert and B. Parris (2022). Fluid transport and storage in the Cascadia forearc influenced by overriding plate lithology, *Nature Geoscience*, <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41561-022-00981-8>.

2.75% (for a cementation factor of 1.3) and between 0.45 – >5% (for a cementation factor of 2.0). Seismic studies also constrain porosity, with average porosity in the Cascadia ETS zone varying from 2.7 – 4% (Peacock, et al., 2011; Bostick, 2013).

Figure 3. (left) locations of land and seafloor MT stations installed under support of the indicated NSF projects (purple markers). The black, yellow and orange markers are publicly available legacy data sets. (middle) Cumulative tremor rates along the Cascadia margin (Hyndman, et al., 2015). (right) Electrical conductance of the 10 km layer above the plate interface. Slab depth contours are plotted as thin black lines. The outline of Siletzia is shown by the green dashed line. MT sites are shown by small white circles.

Figure 4. Vertical sections at two different latitudes (45.0° at left, 42.6° at right) for the 3-D resistivity reference model used in this study. Zones in red are highly conductive, those in blue at highly resistive.

We carried out numerical modeling of the feasibility of a continuously operating MT station array to monitor the cyclic release and migration of slab-derived fluids associated with ETS. We applied constraints on ETS Zone thickness and porosity from seismic models, then modified the cementation factor to determine changes in the electrical resistivity in the resistivity model cells, restricting the changes in the model to a zone only 1 model cell thick immediately above the slab interface in the mantle wedge.

To explore this question, we assembled a hypothetical MT station grid (Figure 5) designed to target detection of changes in the fluid/rock matrix related to ETS and/or megathrust events. To illustrate a key result of this project, we show here only one of many simulations we carried out (Figures 6 and 7), choosing one that involves a perturbation to the cementation factor that is localized to a small geographic footprint rather than across the entire margin, thus more realistic of time-localized ETS, and also more challenging to detect. This simulates a change in the MT response functions that may be related either to a bulk change in fluid volume in the perturbed region at the base of the mantle wedge, or a change in the interconnections in the fluid/rock matrix as a consequence of a stress induced change in the regional strain field that impacts the bulk anisotropy in the fluidic network.

The MT method produces estimates of the MT impedance tensor (a complex-valued frequency domain quantity) that can be scaled into two real-valued, frequency domain quantities, the apparent resistivity and the impedance phase, and it can also be scaled into a third quantity – the phase tensor. In the numerical simulation results below, we show a series of map views of changes in the apparent resistivity and the MT phase tensor vs. period (1/frequency), keeping in mind that the period (in seconds) of these quantities is a proxy for depth of penetration below the surface.

(The MT inverse problem is to transform the MT response function variations vs. period, at each of the MT station locations into estimates of true 3-D electrical resistivity (1/conductivity) at each location within the subsurface.)

Figure 5. (left) Hypothetical MT station locations (triangular blue markers) superimposed on a map of the 3-D baseline resistivity model at a depth of 35 km. **(right)** ETS density (colored square markers) for 2009-2019 overlaid on the resistivity map. White solid lines enclose areas with more than 80 registered ETS event during 2009-2019.

Figure 6. Change in baseline resistivity model (top row) for two vertical sections through the 3-D baseline model (45.0°N latitude at left, 42.6°N latitude at right) by perturbing the cementation factor (Equation 1), decreasing it to a constant 1.5 for ~40 km downdip along the slab interface. The decrease in resistivity results from looser packing of mineral grains and opening or realignment of fluidic channels in the rock/fluid matrix. The ETS layer thickness and the porosity are from the seismic model. The changes are seen in the bottom row.

Figure 7. (left) Map view of the baseline 3-D resistivity model on the curved surface right above the slab/mantle wedge interface. **(right)** map view with a small segment along the central Oregon Margin perturbed by a small change in the localized cementation factor (as in Figure 5).

In Figure 8 the percent change in the apparent resistivity and the phase tensor principal axis at a series of successively longer periods corresponds to successively deeper depths of penetration into the mantle wedge and subducting slab below, at a series of hypothetical MT monitoring station locations above and adjacent to the perturbed area.

Figure 8. (top row) Percent change in apparent resistivity above the perturbed area of the Cascadia margin for periods of 63 s, 398 s and 1000 s revealing variations from the baseline model apparent resistivity of up to 10% at each frequency, a level that is above the typically accepted 5% noise floor for detectability in MT data. **(bottom row)** Change in the phase tensor principal axis

in degrees for periods of 63 and 158 s, revealing variations from the baseline model response of up to 10 degrees, a level that is above the typically accepted 3% noise floor for detectability in MT data.

Conclusions.

Our numerical simulation study reveals that:

- mass fluid volume changes at the subducting slab/mantle wedge interface resulting from redistribution of fluids from mantle dehydration and upwelling, or from
- realignment of the interconnected fluid network along mineral grain boundaries in response to changes in the stress field,

scenarios that are posited to be associated with the ETS cycle, and/or to the inception of a megathrust earthquake phase, produce perturbations to magnetotelluric response functions that exceed the threshold of detectability. This suggests the possibility that a continuously operating monitoring network of MT stations along the Cascadia margin in one or more of the areas identified as highest likelihood for robust ETS cycling, or rupture, may provide insights into the role fluids play in these events, and potentially, a source of data that may improve probabilistic forecasts of such events.

Comments on changes in the project plan.

The project met its major goal, but a subsidiary goal to carry out a formal sensitivity analysis of a hypothetical MT data set by inverting the simulated data with realistic confidence limits on the MT responses, and evaluating the resulting Jacobian matrix proved unfeasible when the project postdoctoral scholar accepted an attractive offer of a faculty position by the Chinese Academy of Sciences Institute of Geology and Geophysics shortly after the November 2024 US election, and departed the following month. The project was completed successfully by the PI, although during a period when he was recovering from major surgery. Nevertheless, the forward modeling exercise was fully accomplished and the many simulation runs demonstrated that even a geographically localized perturbation to the electrical resistivity structure produced theoretically detectable signals at the surface.

Recommended next steps.

A community proposal for a prototype scale continuous MT monitoring program, to cover 2 ETS cycles along the Oregon margin near Newport, Oregon. Such a venture would validate the method using real-world data.

Publications/Presentations. This work was presented at the April 24 2025 Crescent Fluids Interest Group conference in Portland, Oregon, and at the Fall Meeting of the American Geophysical Union in New Orleans, (invited) paper T42A-07, on December 18 2025.